
TRADE POLICY AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF NIGERIA: GLITCHES AND DIAGNOSIS

MARK KINGSLEY CHINONSO, Ph.D

Department of Political Science,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Nigeria

CHUKWUMA OGOONNA .E

Department of Political Science,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Nigeria

SIMONS KWAMIN BENJAMIN

Department of Political Science,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka Nigeria

Abstract

This paper examined trade policy and economic development of Nigeria with references to its challenges and solutions. Developments in both multilateralism and regionalism have raise issues of trade policy strategies. At the country level, it raises issues of which best trade policy strategy to adopt. Consequently, this paper investigated the contemporary issues (factors) affecting Nigeria's trade policy; access trade policy and economic development in the light of GATT and WTO and identify the challenges and prospects of trade policy towards economic growth and development in Nigeria. The review adopted doctrinal method of research. Findings show that neither pure import substitution industrialization (ISI) Strategy nor its export – oriented counterpart would be sufficient to meet Nigeria's quest for rapid economic development. The paper therefore recommends that the government should provide necessary incentives to produce export products. Moreso, the Nigeria's trade policy must be designed within the general context of economic development objectives and goals. An effective trade policy directed at promoting industrial development would necessarily be situated within a strong and well-articulated industrial policy among others.

Keywords: Trade, Policy, Development, Economic Development, Industrialization

Introduction

Trade has long been identified as a veritable way through which the quest of nation for improved well-being of their citizens could be achieved. Adam Smith recommended division of labour, specialization and the pursuit of foreign trade as a way of increasing the wealth of nations Obadan, (2014) and Ajayi, (2015). In support of the assertion, Bakare (2014) went further to state that division of labour was limited by size of the domestic market.

Trade policy is often considered as an essential step for promoting economic growth in the global economy. Despite that the impact of trade policy on economic growth has not been satisfactorily determined, Ezeuchenne (2017) claimed that trade is an important engine of growth for countries at different circles of development, because it contribute to a more efficient allocation of resources and transmission of growth from one part of the country or continent or world to another. Githanga (2015) is of the view that trade liberalization permits inflow of goods, labour, technology, ideas, investment and human capital from one country to another.

Theoretically, the impact of trade on economic growth is that country become more efficient and comparatively more productive by focusing on the production of goods that has comparative advantage. Trade gives room for countries to export goods that were produced from the resources that are domestically surplus and import goods that cannot be efficiently produced from domestic resources because of the scarcity of resources. International trade also permits countries to concentrate and specialize in producing selected ranges of goods and services that give them greater efficiencies of large-scale production.

Krugman (2011) opines that the world is efficient and richer because international trade permits countries to specialize in production of goods or services where countries have comparative advantages and thus reap the gains from external economies. International trade encourages market integration which makes it possible to offer consumers a variety of goods or services at cheaper prices. Trade can occur as a result of increasing returns or economies of scale.

Trade liberalization as an economic policy refers to every attempt that aims at reducing or removing restrictions on international trade and this may include but not limited to the reduction or removal of tariffs, abolition or enlargement of import quotas, abolition of multiple exchange rates and removal of requirements for administrative permits for imports or allocations of foreign exchange. Trade liberalization (openness) promotes foreign direct investment, technology transfer, transfer of goods, services and transfer of capital among countries of the World. No doubt that participation in global markets provides wide range of opportunities for financing investments.

Krugman (2011) says that countries engage in international trade for two cogent reasons, and each of the reasons contributes to their gains from trade. Firstly, countries trade because they are differed in so many ways. Therefore, countries, like individuals, can gain from their differences by reaching a consensus in which each country engages in activity that such country can do comparatively well. Secondly, countries engage in trade in order to achieve economies of scale in production.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria's economy has been largely described as monolithic, owing to an overdependence on its abundance energy reserves. Over the years, the speed and direction of economic growth

and trade has simultaneously been hindered and enabled by the level of oil revenue received. Oil price volatility and revenue unpredictability continues to impact growth performance. Between 2000 and 2014, Nigeria's gross domestic product (GDP) grew at an average rate of 7% per year. Following the oil price collapse in 2014-2016, combined with negative oil production shocks, the gross domestic product (GDP) growth rate dropped to 2.7% in 2015. In 2016 the country suffered its first recession in 25 years and the economy contracted by 1.6%.

Another constraint is fiscal and monetary policy indiscipline. Most times policies and investments made are not profitable and amount to waste of resources. International trade is expected to be beneficial to participants (in form of lower prices, variety of products etc) to firms and businesses (as studies have it that firms exposed to the world's best practices demonstrate higher productivity through many channels such as learning from these best practices thus creating new products and processes in response to this exposure). In the case of Nigeria, it has left our industries in a state of coma as domestic infant industries are destroyed by competition with already established international firms without bringing about a creation of new ones. Hence all these in addition to both fiscal and monetary indiscipline have made the reverse the case in these years.

The dynamics of the Nigerian economy continues to generate considerable interest, particularly the direction of trade and how the government's policies impact the country's economic growth. Like most countries in the world, Nigeria since its independence recognized the need for an effective trade policy, which over the years has evolved with developments on the global scene. And yet economic development and growth through trade has not been noticed. Lastly, various studies have been carried out. Most of which have focused on the impact of trade on various macroeconomic indicators. Very little or nothing has been done to explicitly identify the factors influencing Nigeria's trade. It is against this backdrop that this study investigates trade policy and economic development of Nigeria: glitches and diagnosis.

Aim and Objectives of the paper

The aim of this paper is to examine trade policy and economic development of Nigeria: Glitches and diagnosis, in doing this the aim is mainstreamed to:

- a) Investigate the contemporary issues (factors) affecting Nigeria's trade policy
- b) Identify the challenges and prospects of trade policy towards economic growth and development in Nigeria

Research Methodology of the Study

This review adopted doctrinal method of research. Doctrinal research is an approach which is concerned with the analysis of legal doctrines, principles and rules. In this review, extensive research, analytical study and wide range of scholarly materials were utilized. In view of this, both primary and secondary sources which included textbooks, dictionaries, article journals, internet source materials, laws and other source materials relevant in the course of this work were utilized.

Operational definitions of Concepts

The following concepts are operationalized based on their usage in the context of this paper:

Trade:

Ogunrinola, (2013) define trade as the exchange or buying and selling of goods and services while foreign trade can be defined as commercial transactions (in goods and/or services) across international frontiers or boundaries. Trade Liberalization according to Githanga, (2015) is the removal or reduction of restrictions or barriers on exchange of goods and services between nations. This include removal or reduction of both tariff and non-tariff obstacles. International trade allows the international flow of goods and services, labour and human capital flow from one part of the country to another through immigration. There are also flows of technology, ideas and investment. The effect of trade on productivity is that a country become more productive by allowing the country to produce the things it is good at producing and selling them to other countries in return for other things. Trade Policy implies export promotion and import policy reform.

Policy

Policy is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve rational outcomes. A policy is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocol. Policies are generally adopted by a governance body within an organization. Policies can assist in both subjective and objective decision making. Policies used in subjective decision-making usually assist senior management with decisions that must be based on the relative merits of a number of factors, and as a result, are often hard to test objectively, e.g. work–life balance policy. Moreover, Governments and other institutions have policies in the form of laws, regulations, procedures, administrative actions, incentives and voluntary practices. Frequently, resource allocations mirror policy decisions (Voican, 2018).

Economic development

Economic and social development is the process by which the economic well-being and quality of life of a nation, region, local community, or an individual are improved according to targeted goals and objectives. The term has been used frequently in the 20th and 21st centuries, but the concept has existed in the West for far longer. "Modernization", "Westernization", and especially "industrialization" are other terms often used while discussing economic development. Historically, economic development policies focused on industrialization and infrastructure; since the 1960s, it has increasingly focused on poverty reduction (Finnemore, 2018).

Theoretical Review

Theoretical framework in this study is based upon Harrod-Domar theory and New Endogenous growth model. The theories explained that trade policy leads towards economic growth through various channels. Trade liberalization increases capital inflow which takes several forms like foreign direct investment (FDI). Capital inflow increases investment level in the economy which leads to more production, more output and increases market size. Further increase in production process will cause increase in employment level which reduce poverty.

The Contemporary Issues Affecting Nigeria's Trade Policy

The success of any nation involved in trade, to a large extent depends on her ability to identify and exploit these opportunities, while formulating programmes and policies to stem and/or turn the challenges to opportunities. Nigeria, since independence in 1960 has implemented various regimes of trade policy to strengthen her trade relations. Her trade policy has witnessed tremendous swings from high protectionism within the first decade of independence to the current more liberal stance (Adenikinju 2015).

Trade policy in Nigeria is geared towards promoting manufactured exports and enhancing linkages in the economy. The aim is not only to increase export revenue and reduce the country's reliance on the oil sector, but also to discourage dumping, support import substitution, stem adverse movements in the balance of payment, conserve foreign exchange and generate government revenue (Bankole & Bankole, 2014).

At independence, Nigeria adopted the import substitution industrialization strategy. During the first decade after independence quantitative restriction and high import duties were used to provide protection to local manufacturing industries. Trade policy between 1970 and 1976 became less restrictive due to the post war reconstruction, only items regarded as nonessential consumer goods were restricted. The tariff rates on raw materials were reduced and quantitative restriction placed on spare parts, agricultural equipment and machinery were relaxed. These duties were eventually abolished in 1973 due to oil boom. In 1981, there was a policy shift towards export promotion and a move to intensify the use of local raw materials in industrial production thus tariffs on raw materials and intermediate capital goods were scaled down.

In addition, with the adoption of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986 there was a significant shift in trade policy towards trade liberalization. A seven-year (1988-1994) tariff regime was introduced with the objective of achieving transparency and predictability of tariff rates. This was succeeded by another seven-year (1995-2001) tariff regime. The tariff structure between 1988 and 2001 increased import duties on raw materials and on intermediate and capital goods, while tariffs on consumer goods were slightly reduced. Nigeria's trade policy regime as contained in the national economic empowerment and development strategy (NEEDS) and trade policy documents, is geared towards enhancing competitiveness of domestic industries, with a view to encouraging local value-added and promoting as well as diversifying exports. The mechanism adopted to achieve this is gradual liberalization of trade. Current reforms packages are therefore designed to allow a certain level of protection of domestic industries and enterprises.

The expected impact of trade policy on economic growth in Nigeria is constrained by some diminishing factors which constitute the major problems of international trade. One of the constraints that impact on trade internationally is fiscal and monetary policy put in place by the regulatory authorities. Most of the time, the policies are ineffective, counter-productive and investments made are not viable or amount to waste of resources. Participants in international trade are expected to benefit from lower prices, variety of products and so on. Firms and businesses that participated in international trade are faced with challenge of the world's best practices and this help them to achieve higher productivity because such firms learn from the best practices and also able to create new products and processes as a result of these exposure but reverse is the case in Nigeria. Global trade has left industries in Nigeria in a state of coma as most domestic infant industries are negatively affected due to consumers' preference for the foreign product than that of local industries (Echekoba, Okonkwo & Adigwe 2015).

Moreso, hoarding and secrecy is another major challenge. The essence of trade liberalization is to open up economies in order for the participating countries to learn from themselves and improve product quality and output yet most developed countries are not ready to expose their methods of production and technologies simply for the fear of domination by other countries. Another major challenge to international trade in Nigeria is that most of the countries that are trade partner to Nigeria hoard important commodity and resources which

are needed in Nigeria, yet they get everything they need from Nigeria (Echekoba et. al.2015). This therefore is an indication that trade is not liberalized in action but only in words. Nigeria as one of the developing countries learn close to nothing when it comes to improved ways of doing things, developing countries like Nigeria appeared to be dumping grounds for foreign goods.

Aside from the aforementioned, multiple exchange rates is a big challenge in Nigeria, where official exchange rate by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the black market (parallel market) rate by the Bureau De Change exist side by side and this discourage foreign trade and investment into the country. This existence of the multiple exchange rates obviously has an adverse effect on Nigeria economic growth. Unless all the above challenges are addressed, trade liberalization may not strengthen economic growth in Nigeria.

Trade Policy in Nigeria and Economic Development In The Light Of General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) and World Trade Organization (WTO)

Nigeria's trade policy seem to have recognized the need for an effective trade policy, in the light of GATT and WTO which dictate economic development to a very large extend in the global scene. Notwithstanding the significant role which trade has played in the development of Nigeria, an appreciation of the role and value of a strategic trade policy in the process has been less than satisfactory. This situation partly explains the country's almost total and continuing dependence on a single, raw export commodity, oil.

The proposition here is that unless the country adopts a strategic trade policy stance, it would be difficult for it to realize its goal of diversifying and increasing the value of exports. Nigeria's pre-SAP (Structural Adjustment programme) trade policy had been directed mainly at addressing the problems associated with a deteriorating balance of payments (BOP) Position and, especially, in ensuring an increase in, and easy collection of, government revenue, (Oyejide, 2014). Even when a trade policy was adopted as part of import substitution industrialization (ISI) Strategy, it was still subjugated to the twin objectives of managing the BOP – associated problems and generating government revenue. Indeed, the high tariff walls that had been built in the implementation of the ISI strategy had also served as a source of government revenue and a check on BOP – associated problems; the corresponding trade policy had protected finished goods at the expense of imported raw materials and capital goods.

High tariffs and import license requirements (quantitative restrictions in general) had been the main instruments used to pursue the goals of an ISI strategy. While the Nigerian Federal Government had recognized the dangers of pursuing such an ISI strategy early enough; it had failed to avoid succumbing to the dangers. And most disturbingly, a high-cost industrial economy was emerging, thereby making Nigerian manufactured goods grossly uncompetitive. The success of an export promotions strategy also depends on the formulation and implementation of a strategic trade which has emerged as a viable alternative to the failed ISI strategic, if the support and recommendations of the Brettonwood institutions and the experiences of Japan and other East Asia countries are anything to go by. Although the goal of diversifying Nigeria's export products and markets had been recognized as early as the 1960s, an export – oriented industrialization strategy first received the necessary boost under the structural Adjustment programme (SAP). The corresponding trade policy that had emerged was trade liberalization, through a reduction in tariffs and non-tariff measures, and the creation of export incentives.

A unilateral trade liberalization had been adopted and there had been so much attempt to harmonize it with existing regional trade liberalization policies, under the auspices of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), neither was the trade liberalization (TL) that had been achieved under SAP locked in under the Uruguay Round (UR) (1986 – 1994) multilateral trade negotiations. Similar to the implementation of an ISI strategy and the corresponding restrictive trade policies of high tariffs and quantitative restrictions, the implementation of an export oriented industrialization strategy has been equally faulted on many grounds. It has failed on account of stability as the country is drifting away from the “tariffs only” provision of the WTO. This is evident in the expansion in the list of items on import prohibition and other quantitative measures. Nigeria’s current trade policy lacks transparency, at least on two grounds: (1) The wide gap between bound and applied rate, and (2) the incompatibility of domestic policies and institutions with the WTO standards. There is the need to move from the current “ceiling” binding to ‘floor’ binding and to align the domestic policies and institutions with the WTO standards, if investors and trading partners are to take the country seriously. Nigeria’s scheme of export incentives is also fraught with problems. Government’s export incentives assistance has remained largely general and lacking in focus, uncoordinated and underfunded and, hence, generally ineffective.

Egwaikhide, (1997), has respectively dwelt on different aspects of export promotion in Nigeria and the possible ways of improving performance in the sector. Targeting products for export promotion at the micro level, as is being currently suggested, also raises some challenges relating to the structure of the economy, especially the characteristics of the targeted actors. There must be a deliberate programme of linking the products with the intermediate users at a minimum cost. In the case of the agro-allied chain of production, for example, there is also the need to ensure that farmers will not be penalized as a result of responding positively to the incentives when there is an increase in the demand for their products by the firms that are processing them for export.

One recurring issue is that various government activities point to a lack of coordination among unilateral, bilateral and multilateral efforts. For example, the review of tariff rates, sequel to the expiring of the second seven year tariff regime, is still being awaited, three year after the reviewed edition was supposed to have taken off! It is doubtful if the review would, in any significant way, incorporate the regional agreement at the ECOWAS level, neither is there any assurance that it would take into consideration the ongoing negotiations towards an economic partnership agreement with the European Union. The African Growth Opportunity Act (AGOA) is also not in any way related to other negotiations, similar, multilateral trade negotiations, under the auspices of the WTO, are also taking place separately from, and without any explicit reference to, other levels of negotiations or agreements.

A related feature is that the Nigerian government agencies responsible for these negotiations and trade matters are diverse, and there is no evidence of coordination of their stance regarding issues. The federal ministry of finance is the most prominent agency in the review of custom duties while the new ministry of cooperation and interaction in Africa dictates the tune in matters relating to the ECOWAS and the African Union (AU). The implementation mechanism for taking advantage of the US-led Africa Growth Opportunity Act (AGOA) is under a special Adviser who reports directly to the president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Similarly, a special Adviser is in charge of matters relating to the New Economic Partnership for Africa’s Development (NEPAD), and the federal ministry of commerce is coordinating the country’s position on issues relating to multilateral trade negotiations.

While the routine involvement of various government agencies in the process of initiating and conducting negotiation cannot be ruled out, the lack of coordination and understanding of basic issues and procedures in the terms of the internal workings of the WTO is clearly hampering the effectiveness of integrating the Nigerian economy into the emerging world trading system (Adewale, 2020).

Conclusion

In conclusion, neither a pure import substitution industrialization (ISI) Strategy nor its export – oriented counterpart would be sufficient to meet Nigeria’s quest for rapid economic development. An appropriately mixed strategy, with correspondingly mixed policies and trade policy instruments, is strongly recommended. Such a strategy must be pursued within an integrated frame work and, hence, a coordinated negotiating frame work would be required to make it effective.

The arguments of this part of the discussion and their implications for Nigeria, non-trade objectives, such as peace and security, promotion of good governance and good neighborliness, have tended to dominate the country’s activities at the level of ECOWAS deliberations; effort at coordinating and harmonizing policies, projects, programmes and institutions as pre-requisites for boosting intra-regional trade seem to be a low level priority. There is, therefore, the need to harness the potential for a more robust regional trade and economic integration among member states of the sub-region and explore more actively the benefits from Nigeria’s participation in such arrangement. But Nigeria should also be actively involved at the multilateral level, especially in seeking better market access for its products, pressing for more favourable special and differential treatment, and in defending its rights.

Recommendations

- a) Government should provide necessary incentives to produce export products. Furthermore, to enhance export performance.
- b) The Nigeria’s trade policy must be designed within the general context of economic development objectives and goals. An effective trade policy directed at promoting industrial development would necessarily be situated within a strong and well-articulated industrial policy. Without first determining the overall goal of an economy and the specific role that trade policy would play in the overall scheme, trade policy would be reduced to mere stabilization measures, rather than playing its best suited role of promoting a country’s development in the medium to long run. (Federal Ministry of Commerce, 2000). The emphasis on maximizing government revenue from taxes on international trade seems generally misplaced; the trend is to develop better tax instruments.
- c) Finally, products which give Nigeria a global comparative advantage should be considered for liberalization at the multilateral level. Regional integration at ECOWAS and AU levels should be developed as a stepping stone to opening up the economy to global competition. In this way, the regional trade arrangement would serve as a voice to be reckoned with at the multilateral level, in addition to maintaining security and promoting good governance in the region.

References

- 1] Adenikinju (2015). African Imperatives in the New World Trade Order: Country study of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Ibadan: Finis Publications, 33-34.
- 2] AdewaleAdeagbo (2020). Contemporary Issues in Trade and Trade Policy in Nigeria. Thesis submitted to St. Cloud State University
- 3] Ajayi, K. (2015). *International Administration and Economic Relations in a Changing World*. Accra North, Ghana: Damas Educational Services Limited.
- 4] Bakare, A.S. (2014). The consequences of trade liberalization for economic growth in Nigeria: A Stochastic Investigation. *Contemporary Marketing Review*, 1(14), 14- 23.
- 5] Bankole, A.S. & Bankole, M.A. (2014). Industrial Trade and Export Promotion Policies and Revealed Comparative Advantage in Nigeria's Manufactured Export. Ibadan: University Press
- 6] Echekeba, F.N.; Okonkwo, V. I. & Adigwe, P.K. (2015). Tradeliberalization and economic growth: The Nigerian experience (1971-2012). *Journal of poverty, investment and development*, 14, pp. 51-72.
- 7] Egwaikhide, F.O. (1997). Import Substitution Industrialization in Nigeria: A Selective Review. *The Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 39(2), 183-204.
- 8] Ezeuchenne, K. (2017). International trade and economic growth in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of*
- 9] *Humanities and Social Science*, 22(6), 33-43
- 10] Finnemore, M. (2018). *National Interests in International Society* (5thEdin.). Cornell University Press. pp. 89–97
- 11] Githanga, B.W. (2015). *Trade Liberalization and Economic Growth in Kenya: An Empirical Investigation* (1975-2013). Kenya: Department of Economics, Soderton University.
- 12] Obadan, M.I. (2014). Economic Globalization, Markets and National Development: How sensibly do the poor countries (Nigeria included) stand? Inaugural lecture series. University of Benin, Benin City, September 18.
- 13] Oyejide T A. (2014). *Applied Economics and Economic Policy*. Ibadan: Ibadan University Press.
- 14] Voican, M. (2018). Government's role in coordination of decision making process *Politics. Journal of Political Science*, (17), 26–31.